

Mycobacterial tuberculosis and leprosy in India: a scientometric Study

L R Rahul^a and P Nishy^b

^aResearch Intern, CSIR National Institute for Interdisciplinary Science and Technology (CSIR-NIIST),
Thiruvananthapuram 695019, Kerala, India, E-mail: rahullr999@gmail.com

^bSenior Principal Scientist, CSIR National Institute for Interdisciplinary Science and Technology (CSIR-NIIST),
Thiruvananthapuram 695019, Kerala, India, E-mail: nishy@niist.res.in

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Based on Web of Science data for the period 1987 to 2012, the paper analyses the research carried on mycobacterial tuberculosis and leprosy in India. It is seen that India contributes eight percent to the global research output occupying the third position in terms of quantity of research output and ranks 12th when considering the quality and quantity together. Apart from collaboration pattern, the paper also identifies the major institutions, prolific authors and preferred journals. Three-dimensional performance indicator combining quantity, quality and consistency have been used to rank the productivity of Indian institutions and authors in the field of mycobacterial tuberculosis and leprosy research. From the study it can be concluded that India needs to concentrate more on Mycobacterium research because the cases of tuberculosis and leprosy including multi-drug resistant (MDR) and extensively drug resistant (XDR) strains are emerging each year, and there is a necessity to develop effective controlling programmes for eradicating leprosy.

Keywords: Scientometrics; Mycobacterium; Leprosy; Tuberculosis; Three-dimensional evaluation; Scientific collaboration; India

Introduction

Mycobacterium is a genus of actinobacteria and belongs to the family of mycobacteriaceae. The genus includes pathogens known to cause serious diseases in mammals, including tuberculosis and leprosy¹. Non-tuberculosis mycobacteria (NTM) are the other mycobacteria which can cause the pulmonary disease resembling tuberculosis, lymphadenitis, skin disease, or disseminated disease. *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, the causative agent of tuberculosis (TB), has plagued mankind since the beginning of medical history. It is second only to HIV and AIDS (Human Immunodeficiency Virus and Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome) as the greater killer worldwide due to a single infectious agent². Nine million people fell ill with TB in 2013, including 1.1 million cases among people living with HIV. In 2013, 1.5 million people died from TB, including 3,60,000 among people who were HIV-positive. About five hundred thousand women died from TB in 2013, including 1,80,000 women who were HIV-positive. Of the

overall TB deaths among HIV-positive people, 50% were women. TB is one of the top killers of women of reproductive age. An estimated 5,50,000 children became ill with TB and 80,000 children who were HIV-negative died of TB in 2013². The control of tuberculosis remains elusive as the epidemic of tuberculosis (TB), fuelled by human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) co-infection and increased in resistance to currently available anti-mycobacterial drugs, continues to play havoc in many countries, particularly developing countries. Active immunization or vaccination appear to be an essential component in controlling of tuberculosis, although current vaccine strategies have been ineffective in bringing the disease under control³. There is an urgent need and significant interest in developing new TB drugs.

India and China accounted for 28% and 13% of total TB cases respectively and India accounts for 22% of TB mortality while 3% of deaths occur in China. The number of incident TB cases relative to

population size (the incidence rate) varies widely among countries. The lowest rates are found predominantly in developed countries including most countries in Western Europe, Canada, the United States of America. Southern African countries like Nigeria, Mozambique, South Africa, and Zimbabwe are the most affected with TB. The mortality rate is also high in these countries due HIV positive TB patients (Table 1).

Leprosy is a chronic infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*. Leprosy is one of the world's oldest and most dreaded diseases and it has been synonymous with stigma and discrimination due to the hideous deformities it produced, mystery around its cause and transmission and lack of any effective remedy till recently⁴. Despite the discovery of *M.leprae* more than a century ago and worldwide research since then, several epidemiological features

of leprosy are still poorly understood. In the last two decades, the reported global prevalence of active leprosy infection has dropped by almost 90 percent: yet a parallel drop in the incidence or new case detection rate (NCDR) has not been seen. The number of new cases detected during 2012, as reported by 105 countries, was 232,857 and India topped the list with 57.8 (134,752) per cent to the pool. Population health experts believe that further progress towards eradicating leprosy is dependent on better understanding of new tools to interrupt its transmission. The vaccine that has been studied most in leprosy is BCG. Experience with BCG vaccination for leprosy remains enigmatic in that levels of protection vary from 20 to 80 percent. So, there is a need for an effective vaccine with potential for both prophylactic and therapeutic use to prevent the re-emergence of leprosy and to further help in efforts towards eradication.⁵

Table 1—Global TB Statistics in High Burden Countries by WHO²

Sl. no.	Country	% TB Incidence	% TB mortality	TB mortality to 10000 population	% TB mortality to incidents
1	India	28.38	22.06	2.22	13.24
2	China	13.24	3.31	0.30	4.26
3	Nigeria	7.97	19.44	14.11	41.53
4	Pakistan	6.76	8.02	5.55	20.20
5	Indonesia	6.22	5.39	2.72	14.76
6	South Africa	6.08	7.06	16.86	19.78
7	Bangladesh	4.73	6.37	5.12	22.91
8	Philippines	3.92	2.15	2.75	9.34
9	DR Congo	2.97	4.16	7.76	23.82
10	Ethiopia	2.84	2.83	3.78	16.95
11	Myanmar	2.70	2.40	5.69	15.15
12	Mozambique	1.89	4.44	21.68	40.00
13	Viet Nam	1.76	1.51	2.07	14.62
14	Russian Federation	1.76	1.46	1.29	14.15
15	Kenya	1.62	1.48	4.19	15.50
16	Brazil	1.26	0.52	0.32	6.99
17	UR Tanzania	1.09	0.96	2.46	14.94
18	Thailand	1.08	0.79	1.49	12.50
19	Zimbabwe	1.05	2.20	19.58	35.51
20	Uganda	0.84	0.90	3.01	18.23
21	Cambodia	0.82	0.84	7.00	17.38
22	Afghanistan	0.78	1.04	4.29	22.59

A dramatic decrease has been achieved in the global leprosy burden: from 5.2 million in 1985 to 0.8 million in 1995, and 0.18 million cases at the end of 2013. Global statistics show that 206107 (96%) of new leprosy cases were reported from 14 countries and only 4% of new cases from the rest of the world. Pockets of high endemicity remain in some areas of many countries, but a few are mentioned as reference: Angola, Bangladesh, Brazil, People's Republic of China, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, India, Indonesia, Madagascar, Mozambique, Myanmar, Nepal, Nigeria, Philippines, South Sudan, Sri Lanka, Sudan and the United Republic of Tanzania. The age-old stigma associated with the disease remains an obstacle to self-reporting and early treatment hence political commitment needs to be sustained in countries where leprosy remains a public health problem.

So far no exclusive scientometric study has been carried out on *Mycobacterium* literature. However, a few scientometric studies have been conducted in the past on tuberculosis (TB) and leprosy. Arunachalam and Gunasekaran analysed TB research in India and China from 1990 to 1999 using PubMed, SCI and BSCI databases to identify institutions active in research, journals publishing TB research, the impact of TB research and extent of international collaborations in TB research worldwide⁶. Elangovan analysed 72,390 publications on tuberculosis from 94 countries, published in 3669 journals from the year 1966 to 2001 using MEDLINE database⁷. The author examined the trends and found that there are significantly fewer publications from developing countries, and in journals published from developing countries. Analysis of TB research output by India during 1998-2009 compared with TB research output from China, South Africa and Brazil concluded that India ranks 3rd among the top 21 countries, but its annual publication growth rate and international publication share is lower than the other three countries⁸. An elaborative study carried out using scientometric methods to assess the amount and nature of scientific output in malaria, schistosomiasis and leprosy to compare the amount of research published from developing and developed countries for the three diseases and determining in how far scientometric methods can be used to measure research capacity⁹. The 35,735 publications that appeared in 2874 journals as indexed in PubMed database from 1997 to 2006 were analysed and

compared with population output, GDP and number of incidence of TB cases in different countries and concluded that the countries with more estimated cases of TB produced less research in TB than industrialized countries¹⁰. Ravi and Kumar analysed 1,310 publications on tuberculosis in India over the period of ten years from 1997 to 2006 available in three databases, viz. PubMed, SCI and BSCI. The study identified institutions, cities journals, use of high impact journals and studied the impact of research and extent of international collaboration¹¹. Analysis of 19,201 leprosy publications from 1950 to 2007 using MEDLINE database, shows that the scholarly publications from some of the countries with highest leprosy burden were high¹². PubMed database indexed 3583 leprosy publications from India from 1960 to 2012, the relative growth rate and doubling time of publications were examined in leprosy research at the national level and it was concluded that the rate of publication gradually and steadily grows¹³. There is a rapid growth in HIV/AIDS research from 1992 onwards in India, however, in an international sense, relative productivity of India is low and requires more focused research and development¹⁴. Mapping of tuberculosis research in India identified *International Journal of Tuberculosis and Lung Disease*, All India Institute of Medical Sciences and D. Sriram as the most favoured research journal, major contributing institution and most prolific contributor, respectively during 2004-13¹⁵.

However, we could not find any specific study on mycobacterium causing tuberculosis and leprosy in India analysing the contributions in a three dimensional method. This study focuses on quantity, quality and consistency parameters of each research unit and also maps dynamic changes in the focus field of research on mycobacterium during 1987 to 2012.

Objectives of the study

- To examine the global research distribution pattern in mycobacterial tuberculosis and leprosy;
- To study the growth and relative index of Indian research over the years;
- To examine domestic and international collaboration pattern and its impact in terms of citations per paper;

- To determine the major Indian institutions contributing to Mycobacterial research and rank them on z-index;
- To identify the prolific researchers, major journals and collaborating countries in tuberculosis and leprosy research;
- To examine the co-authorship pattern to identify the major research group engaged in mycobacterium research; and
- To determine the major focus areas of Indian mycobacterium researchers authors and to draw a density diagram.

Methodology

The publication data on *Mycobacterium* was retrieved from Web of Science database of Thomson Reuters. The following search strategy is formed by choosing keywords from MedlinePlus, the National Institutes of Health's Web site. The 79628 records retrieved from the database for the period 1987-2012 are analysed.

Topic = ((mycobacter* OR bovis OR avium OR leprae OR tuberculos* OR lepromatosis) AND (tuberculos* OR leprosy OR scrofula OR mantoux OR hansen's disease OR paratuberculos* OR tuberculin OR johne's disease), Timespan : 1987-2012

The above result set is filtered for India and 6,470 *Mycobacterium* publications by Indian researchers are downloaded based on author affiliation and these records are analysed on the basis of various

quantitative techniques using Bibexcel, Microsoft Excel and represented using Pajek (Program for Analysis and Visualization of Large Networks)¹⁶ and VOSviewer (a software tool for constructing and visualizing bibliometric networks from Leiden University, The Netherlands)¹⁷

Analysis

Country-wise distribution of *Mycobacterium* research papers

There are 79,628 research publications on *Mycobacterium* research in the world during 1987-2012. United States published 23,656 (29.7%) papers followed by UK with 9,041(11.35%) and India with 6,470 (8.12%) publications in this period on *Mycobacterium*. It is interesting to note that most of the *Mycobacterium* research (80%) is done in countries which have lower incidence of TB and leprosy. Only 20% of *Mycobacterium* research is published from the countries with high incidence such as India (8%), South Africa (4%) and China (3%).

When number of publications (P) indicates the quantity of research, we can measure the impact of research as citations received per publication i.e. $i=C/P$, the ratio of total citations(C) to total publications(P). Switzerland published fewer publications than many countries like USA, UK, France, India, Germany etc., but its 2,233 research publications has the highest impact (38.9). The other high impact publications are form Netherland (32.82), and USA (31.97). Figure 1 shows the quality and quantity relationship on top fifteen countries.

Fig. 1—Country-wise distribution of *Mycobacterium* research publications and its impact

Table 2 listed the top performing fifteen countries on *Mycobacterium* research based on Exergy (X), an indicator combining both quantity (P) and quality or impact (i) suggested by Gangan Prathap¹⁴ as $X=iC=C^2/P$ where i=impact, C=citations and P=Publications. USA ranks first, followed by UK and France. India occupies the 12th position. It can also be observed that developed countries have the highest quality of research and developing countries like China, India and Brazil rank lower in *Mycobacterium* research.

Mycobacterium research in India

India is the highest TB burdened country with annual incidences of 2.0-2.4 million cases at 176 (153-193) per 100,000 population. With the implementation of 'Revised National Tuberculosis Control Programme' (RNTCP) by Govt. of India, treatment success has tripled from 25% to 88%, but new cases are still emerging each year. a total of 1,467,585 cases of tuberculosis reported from India in 2012².

India published continuously on *Mycobacterium* and the percentage of publications has gone up from an average of 6% of world output in 1987 to 11% in 2012 (Figure 2). There were a total of 6,470 publications from India during this period comprising journal articles (5,168), review papers (360), editorial

materials (156) and proceedings papers (51). The average impact of review papers (21.87) is more compared to journal articles (13). In the analysis, publications such as correction, discussion, editorial material, letter, meeting abstract, and news items have been ignored.

The relative activity index (RAI), suggested by Frame¹⁸ describes whether a unit is more or less active in their chosen sub-domains than the rest of the world. The number of a unit's publications in a particular sub-domain is divided by the total number of publications from that unit. The same procedure is then done for the rest of the world. To calculate RAI, the share of the unit's publications is divided by the share of the world's publications. The RAI is normalized value to a scale of 0-200 where 100 is equal to the world average which can be expressed mathematically,

$$RAI = 100 + 100 \times (p^2 - 1) / (p^2 + 1) \text{ where, } p = PI/PW;$$

PI=Publications in 'mycobacterium research' in India/Total publications from India and

PW= Publications in 'mycobacterium research' for the world/Total publications in the World.

RAI = 100 indicates that the country's research effort in the given field corresponds precisely to the world's average. RAI >100 reflects higher activity

Table 2—Country-wise distribution of *Mycobacterium* research

Sl. no.	Country	Papers (P)	Impact (i=C/P)	eXergy($X=C^2/P$)
1	USA	23656	32	24184144
2	UK	9041	28	7188908
3	France	5004	26	3324199
4	Switzerland	2233	38	3235177
5	Germany	3798	27	2819680
6	Netherlands	2400	33	2584378
7	Canada	2769	29	2405152
8	South Africa	3285	23	1677440
9	Italy	2433	22	1153104
10	Japan	2804	20	1150828
11	Australia	1772	25	1068254
12	India	6470	12	939906
13	Spain	3084	15	732831
14	Brazil	2480	13	420238
15	China	2491	11	324611

Fig. 2—India's publications in *Mycobacterium* research as percentage share of world output

Table 3—Indian vs. World output and Activity Index in *Mycobacterium* during 1987-2012

Period	1987	1988-92	1993-97	1998-2002	2003-07	2008-12
Papers (as %share of World output)	6.32	6.12	5.05	5.69	8.76	10.32
Impact	13.41	12.83	14.66	16.93	16.24	7.74
RAI of India	181.69	182.70	178.53	182.18	188.24	184.17
eXergy	6649	49408	114840	229402	459908	183239

than the world’s average, and RAI < 100 indicates lower than average effort dedicated to the field under study. RAI for India has been calculated for different years to see how India’s performance changed during different years by using the above formula. Table 3 shows that relative activity index has always been higher than the world average from 178 to 188 and quantity (publications) and quality (impact) of Indian *Mycobacterium* research are also increasing year after year.

Highly productive Indian institutions

There are about 100 institutions engaged in *Mycobacterium* research in India which includes major medical hospitals like All India Institute of Medical Sciences (New Delhi), Post Graduate Institute of Medical Education and Research

(Chandigarh), Christian Medical College & Hospital (Vellore), National Jalma Institute of Leprosy and other Mycobacterial Diseases (Agra), and research institutions such as Tuberculosis Research Centre (Chennai), Indian Institute of Science, (Bangalore), Centre for DNA Fingerprinting and Diagnostics, (Hyderabad), Central Drug Research Institute, (Lucknow), and University of Delhi, (Delhi).The 3-D evaluation proposed by Prathap is used to rank the Indian institutions involved in *Mycobacterium* research. The quantity (productivity in terms of number of publications) and quality (specific impact as defined by citations per publication) are complemented with a third dimension, called consistency η . This enables a better 3-D evaluation of the information production process. If the number of publications is P, the quality or impact(i) is measured

by the ratio C/P , where, C is the total number of citations received by P publications. The product $Exergy(X) = iC = i^2P$ is a robust second-order performance indicator is arguably a better proxy for performance¹⁹. Apart from X , an additional indicator $E = \sum C_k^2$ Where $K=1$ to P , also appears as a second-order indicator. The simple ratio of X to E can be viewed as the third component of performance, namely, the consistency term $\eta = X/E$. Perfect consistency ($\eta=1$, i.e., when $X=E$) is a case of absolutely uniform performance; that is, all publications in the set have the same number of citations, $c_k=c$. The greater the skew, the larger is the concentration of the best work in a very few publications of extraordinary impact. The inverse of consistency thus becomes a measure of concentration. For a complete 3-D evaluation of publication activity, the three primary components, quantity(P), quality(i) and consistency(η) can be used. Using all three components together, a Zynergy (z -index) is computed $Z = \eta X = \eta^2 E$ as $z = Z^{1/3}$ as an energy-like term²⁰.

From Table 4, it is observed that All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS), New Delhi has the highest z -index of 30.59 with 487 publications followed by Tuberculosis Research Centre (TRC), Madras with 416 publications. It is also noted that the

Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Sevagram (Maharashtra) with 42 publications could make the highest impact (27.52) followed by World Health Organization, Regional Office for South-East Asia, New Delhi (24.76) from its 33 publications.

Most of research collaborations in India are between institutions situated geographically nearby. Figure 3 shows the collaboration research among Indian institutions and hospitals on Mycobacterium. There are 56 collaborative research papers between Guru Teg Bahadur Hospital, Delhi and University College of Medical Sciences, Delhi. AIIMS Delhi has research collaborations mainly with Safdarjang hospital (24), JALMA Agra (16), University of Delhi (11), and TRC Chennai (10) on *Mycobacterium* research. IGIB published 26 papers with University of Delhi and ten papers with National institute of Immunology. King George's Medical University collaborated mostly with Sanjay Gandhi Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences and produced 25 research papers in collaboration.

Most prolific authors

The number of multi-authored *Mycobacterium* research publications with more than three authors accounts for 63.81% of the total output indicating the prevalence of team research in this area. There are

Fig. 3—Collaboration map of Indian institutions with more than 60 publications in *Mycobacterium* research

Table 4—Indian institutions with publications in *Mycobacterium* research and its impact

Sl. no.	Institute	Total papers (P)	Papers received citations	Citations received	Impact (i=C/P)	eXergy $X=(C^2/P)$	Consistency ($\eta =X/E$)	z-index [$x=(\eta X)^{1/3}$]
1	All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi	487	448	8857	18.19	161081	0.18	30.59
2	Tuberculosis Research Centre, Chennai	416	391	6989	16.80	117419	0.24	30.57
3	Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Chandigarh	390	347	5349	13.72	73364	0.34	29.23
4	Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore	311	301	4819	15.50	74671	0.37	30.22
5	Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow	200	193	2812	14.06	39537	0.42	25.49
6	University of Delhi, New Delhi	187	174	2663	14.24	37923	0.40	24.66
7	National Jalma Institute of Leprosy and other Mycobacterial Diseases, Agra	175	162	1954	11.17	21818	0.34	19.56
8	National Institute of Immunology, New Delhi	132	127	2092	15.85	33155	0.37	23.16
9	Christian Medical College, Vellore	114	104	1778	15.60	27731	0.27	19.47
10	Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani	104	96	1715	16.49	28281	0.47	23.75
11	Institute of Microbial Technology, Chandigarh	95	95	1395	14.68	20484	0.46	21.08
12	Centre for DNA Fingerprinting and Diagnostics, Hyderabad	93	91	1818	19.55	35539	0.50	26.14
13	Institute of Genomics & Integrative Biology, New Delhi	72	67	1217	16.90	20571	0.44	20.89
14	International Centre for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, New Delhi	66	64	806	12.21	9843	0.58	17.90
15	Bose Institute, Kolkata	64	63	1364	21.31	29070	0.42	22.99
16	Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai	58	53	1203	20.74	24952	0.40	21.48
17	Jawaharlal Nehru Centre for Advanced Scientific Research, Bangalore	49	48	765	15.61	11943	0.66	19.87
18	National Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences, Bangalore	45	43	721	16.02	11552	0.52	18.13
19	Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Sevagram	42	39	1156	27.52	31818	0.31	21.35
20	WHO South-East Asia Regional Office, New Delhi	33	32	817	24.76	20227	0.50	21.58

just 289 single authored publications. The most productive author during the period is Narayanan PR from TB Research Centre, Chennai with 129 publications followed by Katoch VM, Cent JALMA Institute of Leprosy (99 publications), Sriram Dharmarajan, (96) and Yogeeswari P, BITS Pilani (93). Table 5 gives the eXergy, consistency, impact and z-index of 15 leading Indian authors (based on z-index) engaged in *Mycobacterium* research. It is observed that these fifteen authors together contributed 700 quality publications and received a total of 12,598 citations with an average of 17.99 citations per publication. The first eight authors have a higher impact than the average impact (17.99).

Co-authorship pattern

Co-authorship of a paper can be revealed as the collaboration between two or more authors to form a co-authorship network. Bibexcel was used to do co-occurrence analysis to extract author names to list the collaborative pairs, and then do cluster analysis to

identify the sub-networks, which represented different collaborative communities in the whole network. We used Pajek to perform social network analysis to construct the map of the collaboration network and VOS viewer for creating maps based on network data for visualizing. Out of 19,400 authors, 16,100 authors published only one publication, 2002 authors published two, and 580 authors published three publications each and so on.

In order to show the main structure of the network, authors with seven or more publications are included in this integrated analysis. This threshold resulted in a total of 273 prolific authors; among them, 225 authors published co-authorship publications.

These 225 authors formed an undirected co-authorship map visualizing the structure of collaboration network (Fig 4). The Kamada-Kuwai spring embedder in Pajek placed 225 nodes freely from a circular starting position and we repositioned some authors to prevent overlapping labels. Size of

Fig. 4—Co-authorship network in *Mycobacterium* research

Table 5—Most prolific Indian *Mycobacterium* researchers

Sl. no.	Author	Papers (P)	Citations (C)	Impact (i=C/P)	eXergy (X=C ² P)	Consistency ($\eta = X/E$)	z-index= [z=(ηX) ^{1/3}]
1	Narayanan P R TB Res Ctr Chennai	129	670	5.19	3480	0.62	12.95
2	Katoch V M National Jalma Institute of Leprosy and other Mycobacterial Diseases, Agra	99	1168	11.80	13780	0.44	18.26
3	Sriram Dharmarajan Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani	96	1869	19.47	36387	0.40	24.36
4	Yogeeswari P Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani	93	1816	19.53	35461	0.39	24.04
5	Swaminathan S TB Research Center, Chennai	73	920	12.60	11595	0.56	18.69
6	Sharma S K All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi	62	735	11.85	8713	0.34	14.39
7	Chauhan D S National Jalma Institute of Leprosy and other Mycobacterial Diseases, Agra	41	565	13.78	7786	0.42	14.85
8	Tyagi Anil K University of Delhi	38	629	16.55	10412	0.30	14.58
9	Rodrigues C PD Hinduja National Hospital, Mumbai	37	768	20.76	15941	0.45	19.23
10	Singh S V Central Institute of Research on Goats, Uttar Pradesh	36	467	12.97	6058	0.54	14.81
11	Narayanan S TB Research Center, Chennai	32	1696	53.00	89888	0.06	17.15
12	Singh Sarman All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi	26	387	14.88	5760	0.76	16.33
13	Perumal Subbu Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai	21	610	29.05	17719	0.53	21.05
14	Raja Alamelu TB Research Center, Chennai	16	329	20.56	6765	0.62	16.15
15	Misra Amit Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow	15	300	20.00	6000	0.66	15.86
16	Srivastava Brahm S Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow	15	339	22.60	7661	0.46	15.23

the authors vertices are proportional to their number of publications and size the lines linking collaboration pairs with the number of co-authorship publications between the two collaborators. There formed 29

clusters (shown in different colors) and the largest cluster has 36 collaborators, the second largest has 31 collaborators, and the third one has 16 collaborators and so on. Figure 4 depicts the collaboration of

authors in which the network nodes represent authors, and two authors are connected by a line if they have co-authored one or more publications. It is also observed that most of the co-authors are from same institution.

Journals preferred for publication of *Mycobacterium* research

The 6,470 journal articles were scattered in 665 journals. Table 6 gives the list of top fifteen journals preferred by Indian authors for publishing *Mycobacterium* research publications. Among these 15 journals, three are being published from India. Contributions on *Mycobacterium* research in these journals are mainly from Indian authors. The journals are: *Indian Journal of Medical Research* (90%), *Current Science* (88%), *Indian Pediatrics* (79%). *International Journal of Tuberculosis and Lung Disease* topped the list with 276 publications followed by *Indian Journal of Medical Research* with 222 and *PloS One* with 140 publications. India has published a significant percentage of their publications in journals with low impact factor. Only a few publications have appeared in journals with impact factor more than 5.0.

Among the top fifteen journals, *Chest* has the highest impact factor, but only 57 (0.88%) publications by Indian *Mycobacterium* researchers appeared in this journal. It is interesting to note that publications in foreign journals got more impact such as *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*, *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, and *Journal of Biological Chemistry* and so on. A relationship between Impact factor of the journal and the impact of the publications by Indian authors could not be seen.

International collaboration

It is seen that seventeen percent of Indian *Mycobacterium* research out resulted from international collaborations. These collaborations are with 91 countries and most of them received high impact. The strongest collaboration is with United States (7.3%) followed by England (3.6%), France (1.5%), Switzerland (1.5%), Canada (1.2%) and Germany (1.0%). It can be observed from Table 7 that majority of the collaborative partners with India are from developed countries. Publications in collaboration with South Africa had the highest impact (94.33).

Table 6—Preferred journals by Indian *Mycobacterium* researchers

Sl. no.	Journal	Papers (% of total papers)	Impact Factor	Impact (i=C/P)	Place of Publication
1	<i>International Journal of Tuberculosis and Lung Disease</i>	276 (7.9%)	2.756	13.29	Paris
2	<i>Indian Journal of Medical Research</i>	222 (90%)	1.661	10.14	New Delhi
3	<i>PLOS One</i>	140 (13%)	3.534	8.53	San Francisco
4	<i>Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry Letters</i>	104 (38%)	2.331	16.83	Oxford
5	<i>International Journal of Leprosy and other Mycobacterial Diseases</i>	104 (29%)	0	6.87	Greenville
6	<i>Leprosy Review</i>	94 (31%)	0.587	6.02	Colchester
7	<i>European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry</i>	80 (41%)	3.432	23.19	Paris
8	<i>Tuberculosis</i>	80 (11%)	3.503	12.91	Edinburgh
9	<i>Journal of Biological Chemistry</i>	65 (10%)	4.6	20.86	Bethesda
10	<i>Current Science</i>	61 (88%)	0.833	3.61	Bangalore
11	<i>International Journal of Infectious Diseases</i>	61 (17%)	2.33	1.75	Oxford
12	<i>Tubercle And Lung Disease</i>	57 (12%)	0	17.05	Edinburgh
13	<i>Chest</i>	57 (7.4%)	7.132	6.61	Northbrook
14	<i>Journal of Clinical Microbiology</i>	55 (3.2%)	4.232	23.20	Washington
15	<i>Indian Pediatrics</i>	52 (79%)	1.014	3.46	New Delhi

Table 7—International Collaboration in Mycobacterium Research

Sl. no.	Country	Papers (P)	Impact (i=C/P)
1	USA	474	31.03
2	England	234	33.93
3	France	98	38.09
4	Switzerland	97	41.66
5	Canada	80	40.33
6	Germany	67	50.76
7	Italy	60	43.98
8	South Africa	54	94.33
9	Sweden	50	41.02
10	Netherlands	48	66.54
11	Australia	36	49.64
12	China	32	57.38
13	Norway	32	19.88
14	Japan	32	57.84
15	Denmark	28	71.39

Table 8—Major Keywords

Sl. no.	Keywords	1990-94	1994-99	2000-04	2005-09	2010-12
1	Tuberculosis	111	272	577	1240	1124
2	Vaccine & Drug Development	23	66	139	471	547
3	Diagnosis	82	137	217	315	234
4	Immunology	86	141	153	219	204
5	Genetics & Molecular Biology	24	53	132	255	211
6	Drug resistant mycobacterium		12	29	117	213
7	Leprosy	109	118	50	79	0
8	HIV	9	28	53	131	97
9	Cytology	21	25	51	111	60
10	M avium	10		27	74	28
11	M bovis	0	10	19	71	32
12	Epidemiology	6	7	19	43	26
13	M smegmatis	0	8	14	46	26

Areas of research

Keyword analysis reveals that the quantum of leprosy and tuberculosis research carried out during 1990-94 were almost equal (Table 8). Thereafter, the research on leprosy came down. The major portion (50%) of Indian *Mycobacterium* publications is related to tuberculosis. The studies on drug development, diagnosis, HIV, immunology, genetics and molecular biology are other research areas showing positive growth rate.

Highly cited publications

There are sixty one highly cited publications, which received more than 100 citations. One publication received 1,256 citations, two publications received between 501–1000 citations, three between 301–500 citations, five between 201–300 citations and 50 publications between 100–200 citations. Of the 61 highly cited publications, 43 appeared as articles, 15 as reviews, two as conference papers and one Letter. Among these highly cited publications,

Table 9—Highly Cited Papers

Sl. no.	Authors	Article Title	Source	Citations
1	Cohen MS; Chen Y Q; McCauley M; <i>et al.</i>	Prevention of HIV-1 Infection with Early Antiretroviral Therapy	<i>New England Journal of Medicine</i> , 2011, 365(6) Pg.493	1256
2	Boehme C C; Nabeta P; Hillemann D <i>et al.</i>	Rapid Molecular Detection of Tuberculosis and Rifampin Resistance	<i>New England Journal of Medicine</i> , 2010, 363(11) Pg.1005	567
3	Lozano R; Naghavi M; Foreman K <i>et al.</i>	Global and regional mortality from 235 causes of death for 20 age groups in 1990 and 2010: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010	<i>Lancet</i> , 2012, 380(9859) Pg.2095	536
4	Brudey K; Driscoll J R; Rigouts L <i>et al.</i>	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> complex genetic diversity: mining the fourth international spoligotyping database (SpolDB4) for classification, population genetics and epidemiology	<i>BMC Microbiology</i> , 2006, 6	449
5	Gagneux S; DeRiemer K; Van T <i>et al.</i>	Variable host-pathogen compatibility in <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i>	<i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America</i> , 2006, 103(8) Pg.2869	363
6	Pedulla M L; Ford M E; Houtz J M <i>et al.</i>	Origins of highly mosaic mycobacteriophage genomes	<i>Cell</i> , 2003, 113(2) Pg.171	309
7	Vos T; Flaxman A D; Naghavi M <i>et al.</i>	Years lived with disability (YLDs) for 1160 sequelae of 289 diseases and injuries 1990-2010: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010	<i>Lancet</i> , 2012, 380(9859) Pg.2163	281
8	Lalvani A; Nagvenkar P; Udawadia Z <i>et al.</i>	Enumeration of T cells specific for RD1-encoded antigens suggests a high prevalence of latent <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> infection in healthy urban Indians	<i>Journal of Infectious Diseases</i> , 2001, 183(3) Pg.469	253
9	Boehme C C; Nicol M P; Nabeta P <i>et al.</i>	Feasibility, diagnostic accuracy, and effectiveness of decentralised use of the Xpert MTB/RIF test for diagnosis of tuberculosis and multidrug resistance: a multicentre implementation study	<i>Lancet</i> , 2011, 377(9776) Pg.1495	226
10	Salvi S S; Barnes P J	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in non-smokers	<i>Lancet</i> , 2009, 374(9691) Pg.733	207
11	Fine P E M; Ponnighaus J M; Warndorff D K <i>et al.</i>	Randomised controlled trial of single BCG, repeated BCG, or combined BCG and killed <i>Mycobacterium leprae</i> vaccine for prevention of leprosy and tuberculosis in Malawi	<i>Lancet</i> , 1996, 348(9019) Pg.17	204
12	Wright A; Zignol M; Van Deun A <i>et al.</i>	Epidemiology of antituberculosis drug resistance 2002-07: an updated analysis of the Global Project on Anti-Tuberculosis Drug Resistance Surveillance	<i>Lancet</i> , 2009, 373(9678) Pg.1861	190
13	Pai M; Gokhale K; Joshi R <i>et al.</i>	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> infection in health care workers in rural India - Comparison of a whole-blood interferon gamma assay with tuberculin skin testing	<i>JAMA-Journal of the American Medical Association</i> , 2005, 293(22) Pg.2746	190
14	Gajalakshmi V; Peto R; Kanaka T S <i>et al.</i>	Smoking and mortality from tuberculosis and other diseases in India: retrospective study of 43 000 adult male deaths and 35 000 controls	<i>Lancet</i> , 2003, 362(9383) Pg.507	190
15	Chatterji D; Ojha A K	Revisiting the stringent response, ppGpp and starvation signaling	<i>Current Opinion in Microbiology</i> , 2001, 4(2) Pg.160	184

forty were a result of international collaboration, nine were published in *Lancet* and four in *New England Journal of Medicine*. A list of the top 15 most cited publications is given in Table 9.

Conclusion

Mycobacterium is the causative agent of widespread diseases, including tuberculosis and leprosy. India is the country with the highest burden of tuberculosis and one of the countries with the high number of new leprosy diagnoses. The Programmes like Revised National Tuberculosis Control Programme (RNTCP) for controlling Tuberculosis and National Leprosy Eradication Programme for eliminating leprosy by India has been successful to an extent yet new cases are reporting each year.

Mycobacterium research in India shows a positive growth, positioning India in the 3rd place with respect to quality of research output. India is at the 12th position when the countries are ranked on the basis of eXergy (X). The research collaboration with other countries resulted in 17% high-quality research output.

While tuberculosis research in India grew rapidly, leprosy research has been on the decline even though leprosy cases are reported from India as per WHO statistics. India needs to concentrate more on *Mycobacterium* research because the cases of tuberculosis and leprosy including multi-drug resistant (MDR) and extensively drug resistant (XDR) strains are emerging each year, and there is a necessity to develop effective controlling programmes for eradicating leprosy.

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